

Studies of Some Reactions on 3-Hydroxy-6-Chloro Coumarin

D. Chakravarti, R. Das and (Mrs.) Minati Saha

The present work deals with the study of some reactions such as nitration, formylation, coupling with diazotised aniline and condensation with formaldehyde on 3-hydroxy-6-chloro coumarin, a considerable amount of which was synthesised by the authors¹.

3-Hydroxy coumarin was shown to exist in keto-enol tautomeric forms by Erlenmeyer and Stadlin². From the pattern of substitution studied by Trivedi and Sethna³, it is revealed that the position 4 in 3-hydroxy coumarin is mainly responsible for the chemical reactivity of the molecule.

Nitration : From the results of previous investigations³, it was thought that nitration might furnish a 4-nitro coumarin derivative. It may be mentioned that a coumarin with nitro group in 4-position is hitherto unknown. But nitration of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro coumarin (I) with fuming nitric acid and acetic anhydride under the specific condition used underwent degradative nitration, already referred by Das⁴ in a short communication, giving 2, 6-dinitro-4-chloro phenol (II) identified from elementary analysis, IR and N.M.R. data.

The N.M.R. spectrum of the product showed two proton signals : one at $\tau-1.25$ (for one proton) and another at $\tau+1.73$ (for two protons). The highly deshielded proton peak at $\tau-1.25$ for one proton could be attributed to $-OH$ highly chelated due to vicinal nitro group. IR spectrum (Nujol) γ_{max} 3100, 1640, 1580, 1560, 1260, 1160 cm^{-1} .

The appearance of hydroxy band at 3100 cm^{-1} indicated strong hydrogen bonding (The parent compound¹(1) shows $-OH$ band at 3350 cm^{-1} . The absence of δ -lactone carbonyl band shows the rupturing of the pyrone ring)

It is presumed that the product (II) has been formed by opening of the lactone ring, oxidation of the unsaturated side chain and its replacement by nitro group. Further nitro group is introduced in the available position of increased electron density. It is mentioned

1. D. Chakravarti and R. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1971, **48**, 371.
2. E. Erlenmeyer and W. Stadlin, *Ann.* 1904, **337**, 283.
3. K. N. Trivedi and S. Sethna, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1817.
4. R. Das, *Science and Culture*, Communicated, 1971.

here that 4-hydroxy coumarin under identical condition gave 3-nitro coumarin derivative as studied by Josef Klosa⁵.

Formylation : Spath and Pailer⁶ observed the failure of Gatterman reaction and Reimer Tiemann reaction on hydroxy coumarins. However, they succeeded in formylating 7-hydroxy coumarin by the use of hexamine as in Duff and Bills⁷ method and obtained the 8-formyl derivative. Later, a number of workers used hexamine as formylating agent for hydroxy coumarins having hydroxy group or groups in benzene nucleus^{8,9}. Ziegler and Maier¹⁰ obtained 3-formyl derivative by treating 4-hydroxy coumarin with N-methyl formamide in presence of phosphorous oxychloride. But no attempt has so far been made to introduce a formyl group in 4-position of 3-hydroxy coumarins. The present work shows that hexamine is successfully used as a formylating agent in the case of (I) giving rise to a 4-formyl derivative (III) in poor yield. This gave an orange 2 : 4- D.N.P.H derivative. The introduction of the formyl group in the α -pyrone ring was proved by oxidation of (III) to 5-chloro salicylic acid with alk. KMnO_4

The IR data (given under experimental) also support the structure (III).

Coupling with diazotised aniline : It has already been reported by the authors¹ that 3-hydroxy coumarins couple with diazotised solution of aromatic amines giving brilliant red azo dyes. In order to elucidate the structure of the azo compound thus formed, the action of diazotised aniline on (I) was studied in detail. The interesting observation is noted below.

The compound (I) in alkaline solution was found to couple readily with diazotised aniline giving a bright red coloured azo dye which could not be crystallised. On exposure to air to get an air dried product, it was observed that the colour of the compound began to fade gradually from red to light orange in course of two days. This gradual change of colour has been attributed to the fact that the azo compound (IV) has undergone a molecular rearrangement giving rise to 2 : 3- diketo-4-phenyl hydrazo-6-chloro chroman (V).

5. Josef Klosa, *Pharmazie*, 1953, **8**, 221
6. Spath and Pailer, *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 940.
7. J. C. Duff and E. J. Bills, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1932, 1987
8. S. Rangaswami and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad., Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 112.
9. R. M. Naik and V. M. Thakor, *J. Org. Chem.* 1957, **22**, 1626.
10. E. Ziegler and H. Maier, *Monatsh*, 1958, **89**, 787.

The assignment of structure (V) to the compound was supported by its formation of a condensation product with ortho-phenylene diamine. The change of colour of the azo compound together with the formation of the quinoxaline derivative with ortho phenylene diamine proved that the phenyl hydrazo residue has occupied the position 4. To support the above structure (V) it may be pointed out that Dimorth¹¹ and many other investigators have studied the coupling reactions of aromatic amines on keto-enol tautomers. This is often used to detect the presence of the enolic form in the keto-enol mixtures and is then referred as the Japp-Klingemann reaction. This type of molecular rearrangement has also been reported in the case of the coupling of 4-hydroxy coumarin with diazotised amines by Hubner and Link¹² and supported by Okumara¹³.

Condensation with formaldehyde: Condensation of formaldehyde with 4-hydroxy coumarin gives dicoumarol having antibacterial and anticoagulant properties. Trivedi and Sethna³ have shown that the formaldehyde condensation is applicable in the case of simple 3-hydroxy coumarin giving 4, 4'-methylene-bis-(3-hydroxy) coumarin. The authors have applied this reaction on a halogenated 3-hydroxy coumarin derivative. Thus (I) on treatment with formaldehyde (40% solution) in presence of mineral acid (catalyst) gave 4, 4', methylene-bis-(3-hydroxy-6-chloro) coumarin (VI) which may be oxidised to 5-chloro salicylic acid by alk. KMnO_4 .

It was expected that this compound with two hydroxy-chloro coumarin nucleus bridged by a methylene group might have physiological activity. But it has been found to be inactive against bacteria, (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Aerobacter aerogenes*) and fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Tricophyton rubrum*). The action of (VI) against microorganisms was tested by usual Agar-streak and serial dilution method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitration of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro coumarin: Coumarin derivative (I) (2g) was very slowly added to a well cooled mixture of acetic anhydride (4 ml) and fuming nitric acid (5 ml sp.gr. 1.5). The coumarin derivative rapidly went into solution in the nitrating mixture giving rise to a brown solution. Temperature was kept below 5° during addition. On completion of addition which required about an hour, the mixture was gradually brought to the room temperature and kept for 16 hrs. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice water with vigorous stirring and allowed to stand overnight. The yellow product

11. Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 2404.
12. Charles F. Hubner and Karl Paul Link, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1945 **LXVII**, 99.
13. Okumara, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1961, **81**, 307.

which separated was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from 50% alcohol as yellow needles. The m.p. and mixed m.p with an authentic sample of 2, 6-dinitro-4-chloro phenol was 81°: Yield 0.3 g.

Found : C, 32.48 ; H, 1.60 ; N, 12.58 ; calculated for $C_6H_3O_6N_2Cl$; C, 32.95, H, 1.37%, N, 12.81.

The product was homogeneous by T.L.C. (Rf 0.79 ; solvent used : butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 2 : 1).

4-Formyl-3-hydroxy-6-chloro coumarin (III) : To a mixture of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro coumarin (4 g) and hexamethylene tetramine (8 g), glacial acetic acid (80 ml) was added and the mixture was heated on a steam bath for 8 hrs. A hot solution of Conc. HCl (60 ml) and water (60 ml) was then added and heating on the waterbath was continued for 2 hrs. It was then cooled and extracted with ether. On removal of ether and the residual acetic acid a semi solid brownish mass remained, which solidified on standing for a few hours. The solid was crystallised from aqueous alcohol as colourless crystals melting at 215° (not sharp), yield 0.9 g. Sublimation at 160° under 0.2 mm pressure gave a pure product m.p. 220°. The alcoholic solution of the substance gave greenish colouration with $FeCl_3$.

Found : Cl, 15.51% ; $C_{10}H_5O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 15.81%. 2 : 4-D.N.P.H. derivative (acetic acid) melted. at 239-40°(d). Found : N, 13.35%, $C_{16}H_9O_7N_4Cl$ requires N, 13.84%. IR spectrum (Nujol) ν_{max} 3350 cm^{-1} (—OH), 1710 cm^{-1} (δ -lactone), 1690 cm^{-1} (aldehydic function), 1645, 1610, 1565 cm^{-1} (aromatic residue).

Oxidation of the above formyl compound : $KMnO_4$ (1 g.) in water (20 ml) was added dropwise to a hot solution of (III) (0.5 g.) in 10 ml of sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 3 hrs. The mixture was cleared with SO_2 , acidified and extracted with ether. The residue left on evaporation of ether was dissolved in 5% $NaHCO_3$ solution. The alkaline solution on acidification precipitated 5-chloro salicylic acid which was crystallised from hot water m.p. 170°. No depression in m.p. was observed on admixture with an authentic sample of the acid prepared by the method of Weil *et al*¹⁴.

Coupling of (I) with diazotised aniline : (2, 3-diketo-4-phenyl hydrazo-6-chloro chroman) (V) : To a suspension of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro-coumarin (1.5 g) in ethanol (10 ml) was added crystalline sodium acetate (7.5 g) and water (5 ml). The mixture was cooled to 0° and with stirring a diazotised solution of aniline (1 ml) in HCl (5 ml) and water (10 ml) was added. Immediately a bright red solid appeared. Stirring was continued for 1 hr. more and the reaction mixture kept in an ice bath for half an hour. The red coloured mass was filtered with gentle suction and washed with water. After a while, the red colour began to fade and in course of about 48 hr. the red mass was converted into a light orange solid, which was crystallised from methanol as light orange needles, m.p. 180°. Yield 0.9. Found : N, 9.6%, $C_{15}H_9O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.31%.

Condensation of (V) with o-phenylene diamine : An alcoholic solution of the ortho phenylene diamine (.2 g) was added to a solution of the above product (.5 g) in absolute alcohol. The reaction mixture water refluxed on water bath for 30 minutes and cooled.

14. Weil, Traun, Marcel, *Ber*, 1922, 55, 2665.

The solid obtained on dilution with water was crystallised from acetic acid m.p. 275-76°(d). Found : N, 14.14%, $C_{21}H_{13}ON_4Cl$ requires N, 15.03%.

4, 4'-methylene-bis-(3-hydroxy-6-chloro) coumarin : The compound (I) (1 g) in alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 hrs. on a water bath with formalin (3 ml) and 3 drops of Conc. HCl. The solid product separated was filtered hot. The residue crystallised from alcohol gave colourless needles melting at 287-80°.

Found : Cl, 17.75%. $C_{19}H_{10}O_6 Cl_2$ requires Cl, 17.53%.

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Department of Pure Chemistry,
University College of Science and Technology,
Calcutta-9.

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